

Deliverable D7.3

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1 Executive Summary

Deliverables 7.1 and 7.2 provided a workshop and an ontology (DIAB) for Type 2 Diabetes (T2D) and evaluated the use of the DIAB ontology annotation and query for TD2 data. Here we evaluate the ontology as an extension of a semantic matching service (PhenoDigm, <http://www.sanger.ac.uk/resources/databases/phenodigm/>) to test whether the ontology improves recall of mouse models of T2D using three gold standard T2D associated gene lists for the evaluation and comparing DIAB's T2D associated phenotype list to DIAB subsets, and other available T2D associated phenotype datasets.

2 Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives:

No.	Objective	Yes	No
1	Identify and develop a set of annotations, necessary terminologies, and mappings between terminologies for human and mouse models of diabetes and obesity		X
2	Identify and group related interacting parameters in human and mouse which are involved in the development of clinical and molecular phenotypes		X
3	Formalise rules for phenotypic annotation in human and mouse to work towards automation of phenotypic discovery and develop a related prototype service	X	

3 Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Introduction

Mouse models are a critical tool for translational researchers and access to rich information about phenotypes as well as genotype informs translational researchers in selecting a mouse strain for future experiments. However, different representation of human and mouse phenotypes, and understanding the relationships between measured phenotypes and disease presents a challenge in translation of mouse data to human researchers. Our chosen disease area is Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2D) – previously referred to as non-insulin dependent diabetes or adult-onset diabetes, a common chronic disease affecting 9% of adults in 2014 that continues to increase in numbers and significance. Disease etiology is a combination of resistance to insulin action and an inadequate compensatory insulin secretory response that is exacerbated with obesity. The World Health Organization (WHO) projects that diabetes will be the 7th leading cause of death in 2030. We sought to improve the ontological representation of T2D and related phenotypes using both mouse and human phenotype ontologies and propose a rapid and lightweight process for ontology development enabling domain experts to contribute directly to ontology development without recourse to ontology editing tools. Our aim is to generate improved representation of disease associated phenotypes by providing an improved ontology as an input to the PhenoDigm resource, particularly for non-Mendelian diseases. PhenoDigm uses a semantic similarity measure to identify commonalities in phenotypes between strains of model species and calculates their overlap with clinical features of human disease. A phenotype score is given to capture how well a disease model recapitulates the phenotypes associated with a human disease population. In this it is limited by the available ontologies used for comparison. The first step in the process was a community workshop (reported in Deliverable 7.1) in which domain experts and ontologists reviewed existing ontology content for completeness, structure and appropriateness for the

domain. Four widely used resources were identified as relevant for description of T2D, its stages and associated phenotypes. These were the Human Disease Ontology (DO), the Human Phenotype Ontology (HP), Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man – OMIM and the Experimental Factor Ontology, which imports the Orphanet Rare Genetic Disease Classification from the Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology (ORDO), and the Mammalian Phenotype Ontology (MP). While the human DO provides a disease-focused scaffold of standardised common and rare disease concepts, it does not include the progression or the manifestations within its disease definition that are critical for representing the varied clinical features associated with T2D. Disease associated phenotypes are represented in multiple resources, for example Unified Medical Language System (UMLS) or OMIM but these are not exhaustive, for example UMLS does not yet include HP, though this is planned. HP describes abnormal human phenotypes and has mappings to other phenotypes sources such as London Dysmorphology Database, Orphanet, MedDRA, UMLS, and phenoDB. MP is the standard resource for mammalian phenotype descriptions used by curators at Mouse Genome Informatics (MGI), the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC) analysis pipeline and by the Monarch project. MP therefore integrates literature and analytical pipelines on phenotyping experiments on mammalian model species. EFO is an application-based ontology developed at EBI initially to aid annotation of Gene Expression data, but increasingly supporting integration of other biomedical data. EFO imports HP, ORDO amongst others and cross references DO; concepts are enriched through axiomatisation by linking them to concepts such as anatomy and cell-line but diseases and phenotypes are not connected. OMIM is the largest database providing information on all known Mendelian disorders and over 15,000 genes. OMIM focuses on the relationship between phenotype and genotype but also provides other critical information in textual description, limiting its utility for computation. The workshop participants concluded that while all the resources examined deliver some components of the knowledge in the domain, these are insufficiently integrated and critical information is missing. For example the temporal nature of the disease in stages is not described in any of the

resources, the core phenotypes enabling diagnosis vs. those associated with late stage complications were unavailable, and there is no complete and explicit representation of T2D phenotypes associated with the disease. We have therefore integrated and extended existing ontologies to create T2D-specific ontological resource, with cross-references to existing ontologies using a text mining approach. In this deliverable, we describe the use and evaluation of the ontology of T2D associated phenotypes (reported in D7.2) in the PhenoDigm tool using known genes associated with T2D as a reference to test whether the ontology improves recall of mouse models. We also compared the T2D associated phenotypes with other available T2D associated phenotypes.

3.1.1 PhenoDigm

PhenoDigm uses a semantic approach to map between clinical features observed in humans and mouse phenotype annotations. It uses the human and mouse phenotype ontologies HP and MP and the OWL-Sim algorithm to compare ontologies. In this experiment, we used a test version of PhenoDigm configured to use the datasets and phenotype associations described here. The production implementation of PhenoDigm is hosted at the Wellcome Trust Sanger Institute (<http://www.sanger.ac.uk/resources/databases/phenodigm/>) using different ontologies) and is used in delivery of the IMPC Data Portal <http://www.mousephenotype.org/> where it provides matches between human disease phenotypes and mouse disease models for the Knockout Mouse Project 2, IMPC and MGI literature curated datasets.

3.1.2 Experimental Design

To test the DIAB ontology's ability to retrieve mouse models using PhenoDigm we used the production version of PhenoDigm running on a test server, version 2 of the DIAB ontology and three different lists of T2D associated genes. It is hard to obtain a canonical set of known T2D associated genes to use as a benchmark, and so we tested three sets to examine performance vs.

gene sets of different size and source. These gene sets are described below and summarised in Table 1.

Table 1 Gold standard Gene Sets used in DIAB test

GeneSet	Size	Date Accessed/Version
CTTV	279	November 2015
MGI	21	November 2015
BMB Curated Set	112	July 2015

The DIAB T2D associated phenotypes represent the complete set of phenotypes we detected and verified through expert curation, but there are other sets of T2D associated phenotypes available. Therefore to complete the comparison we identified two subsets of DIAB, and two external sets of T2D associated phenotypes and compared DIAB with these. These are described in 3.1.2.4 and summarised in Table 2. By testing multiple gene sets and also externally source T2D associated phenotypes we provide a comprehensive evaluation of DIAB.

3.1.2.1. CTTV T2D associated gene set

The Centre for Therapeutic Target Validation (CTTV, <http://www.targetvalidation.org>) is a collaborative project providing gene-disease or gene-phenotype associations from multiple biomolecular databases including Uniprot, ClinVar, Reactome, GWAS and ChEMBL. It therefore provides a unified representation of these resources using common gene and disease identifiers, and also an association score based on whether evidence for a gene-disease association is present in multiple data sets, protein, pathways, GWAS etc. CTTV contains gene-disease associations mined from the literature, but for the purposes of this experiment only curated gene-disease associations from existing knowledge bases were used as the aim was to use CTTV data from a unified and curated source. The CTTV dataset is scored using a cumulative score for each source of evidence e.g. from a different data resource or from different datasets. We used T2D associated

genes with a score of 4 or above for the evaluation, as these are genes that show a strong association with T2D. This gene set consists of 279 genes.

[3.1.2.2. MGI T2D Associated Genes](#)

MGI based at the Jackson Laboratory provides a curated list of gene-disease associations derived from the scientific literature. This curator asserted list of T2D a gene models does not necessarily imply that the phenotypes are matched between the mouse and human models, rather that the author of a manuscript asserts that a mouse strain with a mutated gene is associated to T2D. The data curated from the literature are also subject to strain and experimental variation as they are not generated from a coordinated experiment, and do not necessarily represent a complete view of genes from the literature.

[3.1.2.3. BMB Literature curated T2D Associated genes](#)

We performed literature review of a series of review articles to manually generate and validate a list of high confidence genes associated with T2D. Review articles were manually retrieved from EuropePMC and included genes identified from GWAS studies.

[3.1.2.3. Ontology Comparisons](#)

DIAB was generated using text mining and expert input (Reported in D7.2) and consists of disease-phenotype associations with disease stage information. Some of the T2D associated phenotypes are also associated with other diseases and we hypothesized that this may generate noise in the comparison with other ontologies. Therefore three sets of T2D associated phenotypes representing different subsets of DIAB were compared to each gene set described above and to two other disease-phenotype semantics resources during it evaluation. This is summarised in Table 2 and Figures 1-2. Briefly:

- All 184 T2D associated phenotypes represented DIAB were used including those associated with prediabetic states that will manifest into T2D and late stage complications of T2D (row 1, Table 2)

- The set of 28 DIAB Phenotypes determined to be highly relevant to T2D by manual curation by a clinical expert (row 2, Table 2)
- The manifest_in T2D associated phenotypes from DIAB. Manifest_in relationship denotes all phenotypes associated with manifest T2D and not, for example, prediabetic states or late complications (row 3, Table 2).
- Recent work by Groza et al.¹ has used a similar process to mine HP annotations for a wider set of diseases including T2D. We therefore performed a comparison of the outcomes for this study and that of Groza et al. The tab-delimited file containing disease-phenotype annotations was downloaded from: http://pubmed-browser.human-phenotype-ontology.org/hp_common_annotations_all.tab (accessed October 2015) and the results compared (row 4, Table 2).
- The original HP-T2D phenotype association set currently available in the production version of PhenoDigm (row 5, Table 2).

Table 2 Ontologies and dataset comparisons used as input to PhenoDigm in evaluation of DIAB

	T2D associated phenotypes	Size	Gold Standard Set 1	Gold Standard Set 2	Gold Standard Set 3
1	All T2D DIAB associated phenotypes mapped to HP	184	CTTV Set	MGI Curated Annotations	BMB Set
2	'Essential' T2D DIAB associated phenotypes	28	CTTV Set	MGI Curated Annotations	BMB Set
3	Manifest_in phenotypes associated with T2D	278	CTTV Set	MGI curated annotations	BMB Set
4	All <i>Groza et al</i> terms associated with T2D	171	CTTV Set	MGI curated annotations	BMB Set

¹ <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0002929715002347>

5	Original HPO phenotypes associated with T2D	2	CTTV Set	MGI curated annotations	BMB Set
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The T2D phenotypes from different sources have considerable overlap. The two HPO terms currently used by PhenoDigm (insulin resistance and Type 2 diabetes mellitus) are contained in all the other T2D associated phenotype sets. The manifest_in and essential sets are subsets of DIAB determined by clinicians, and Groza et al and DIAB T2D associated phenotypes have an overlap of 108 terms. As the processes used to generate the terms are similar for the latter two sets, it may be expected that the overlap should be larger. Analysis of the phenotype terms in each set indicate that some of the overlap results from different versions of HP used in the analysis, and the remainder of derives from the use of the Mammalian Phenotype Ontology as a text mining dictionary which significantly increases the number of terms associated with T2D in DIAB over Groza et al (see Table 1). As the DIAB terms were curated and categorised by experts, we are confident that these terms represent a more complete representation of T2D associated phenotypes. The overlaps between the T2D phenotype associated datasets are visualised in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1 Venn Diagram showing the overlap between DIAB all T2D associated phenotypes, DIAB manifest-in phenotypes, and DIAB essential phenotypes

Figure 2 Venn Diagram showing the overlap between DIAB and Groza et al associated phenotypes

4 Results

PhenoDigm was run on each of the T2D HPO annotation files to search for phenotypically similar mouse models present in two existing datasets: MGI and IMPC. The genes associated with these mouse models were ranked by the PhenoDigm similarity score² and compared to the 3 gold standard datasets described in Table 2. Receiver operator characteristic (ROC) plots of true positive versus false positive rates for each comparison were generated and the area under the curve (AUC) used to assess which HPO annotation set was most useful for recalling known genes associated with T2D for each dataset. A graph was produced for each gold standard dataset.

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² <http://database.oxfordjournals.org/content/2013/bat025.short>

4.1 CTTV Dataset

Figure 3 All ontologies compared vs. the CTTV dataset

4.2 MGI curated dataset, multiple ontologies

Figure 4 All ontologies compared vs. MGI curated TD2 associations

4.3 BMB Dataset, multiple ontologies

Figure 5 All ontologies compared vs. manually curated BMB dataset

5 Conclusion

The results indicate that when compared to the CTTV dataset, the DIAB dataset, the manifest in component of DIAB, and the Groza et al. dataset all perform similarly in recalling known T2 genes, and return more accurate results than the curated most essential DIAB terms, or the HPO provided annotations. These results are reversed for the BMB and MGI curated datasets where the essential ontology terms and the original HPO terms perform better. This is to be expected as we are essentially comparing a small gene set of known genes with a set of phenotypes which are tightly linked to T2D and this is better represented by HP and essential DIAB where a subset of phenotypes are tested. The ROC are very close together for this dataset, and therefore we conclude that this gold standard set is too small to be an effective tool in evaluating DIAB. The CTTV dataset has many more data points and DIAB performs better here, and is able to identify what we assume are more weakly associated T2D models in this large dataset. As in future we

expect the available datasets to be very large and to have many phenotypes annotated, the ability to perform well with large datasets is desirable and the performance of DIAB vs. the CTTV dataset represents an improvement in the state of the art over the current PhenoDigm Implementation for T2D related models. The current use of PhenoDigm is to provide matches to models for human review and some performance differences by dataset are therefore acceptable for this use case. Future work will evaluate the differences for further work to assemble a more comprehensive test set, and a publication will be submitted describing this work. For example, we will evaluate performance if we merge the test gene sets that have little overlap and investigate adding CTTV literature mined datasets. We also hypothesise that the relatively large size of DIAB and Groza et al T2D phenotype associated datasets introduce noise that results in reduced performance when tested against small gene sets, and will design an experiment to test this. Another test will be to compare the T2D phenotypes from DIAB with those for other diseases and to refine the phenotypes into combinations of phenotypes associated with T2D to investigate if this improves performance.

We have developed an improved ontological representation of expert knowledge about T2D based on a simple text mining and expert review process. The process used provides a pragmatic method to extract information from the literature, present it to domain experts for review who then refine the association type to more precisely represent the domain. We have found text mining to be a useful tool in building ontologies, and specifically for making associations between ontologies using the literature, here between disease and phenotype. The process has since been used successfully to perform disease-phenotype association in different disease areas with new domain experts and applied more widely. In our comparison of two text mining approaches, we observe that combining terms from both mouse and human phenotype ontologies provides a richer representation of human phenotypes both for the T2D work presented here and also in a similar experiment for Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD) where 102 IBD associated phenotypes were mined and validated using the same pipeline with MP terms. Our study agreed with Groza et al. for 60% of T2D phenotype associations, and our

clinical experts added very few terms. We note that our process was likely aided by a corpus of literature for T2D from specialist journals and use of MP, which presumably is the reason only two additional T2D-phenotype associated terms were added by domain experts during review. One of these terms ‘macular edema’ is now present in HP, but was not when the text mining was performed and was therefore not retrieved. The second, ‘hyperosmolarity’ is present in Snomed-CT as a child of ‘metabolic finding’ and as a compound term with T2D in MEDRA [T1] but is absent from both from versions of HP and MP used in the text mining and current versions. Our next steps are to ask our experts to review those terms that Groza et al, retrieved which we did not, and to include those they verify in both the OBAN representation with provenance, and in an updated version of DIAB. A mapping of terms between the two mouse and human ontologies is underway and new terms have been requested for HP based on our text mining results with MP. Future improvements to our text mining process include sub-selection of ontology terms e.g. excluding upper level nodes to reduce noise for experts. The ontology is available in OWL and also transformed into the OBAN framework as a generic phenotype-disease association for community use. OBAN - Open Biomedical Annotations is a generic representation used to describe associations between biomedical entities and provides a representation which can be qualified in future. For example frequency information could be added, as could evidence strings corresponding to different curators, or curatorial processes. These are hard to model in an ontology, and OBAN is a more flexible way to model these. Improvements to the ontology representation include capture of the relevance level of each phenotype for each disease stage and the use of an upper level ontology such as BFO. The OWL representation contains phenotypes associated with ‘disease other than diabetes’ by the domain experts. A better representation would be to specify which diseases the phenotypes are associated with. Our work represents a process to connect phenotype to disease using HP and MP terms and the involvement of experts is critical. Our motivation to do this is derived from involvement in the IMPC where we collect mouse model data based on observed phenotypes, and wish to connect these to human phenotypes to

better model disease processes for both rare and common disease. Finally a manual mapping between the HP and MP phenotype terms we have detected is underway and new term requests have been made for HP.

Supplemental information for this work are available from <https://github.com/EBISPOT/T2D>.

6 Delivery and schedule

The delivery is delayed: Yes No

7 Adjustments made

No adjustments were made to the deliverable.

8 Background information

This deliverable relates to WP 7; background information on this WP as originally indicated in the description of work (DoW) is included below.

WP 7 Title: PhenoBridge-crossing the species bridge between mouse and human

Lead: Michael Raess (HMGU)

Participants: EMBL, HMGU, MUG, CIRMMMP

This demonstrator project tackles a major challenge related to the available mouse phenotype and human clinical data: different ontological phenotype descriptions hinder researchers from both sides to cross the species bridge between mouse models and human. We will make use of comparable diabetes and obesity-related large-scale datasets in mouse and human provided by

Infrafrontier, BBMRI and ELIXIR.

To achieve integration at the level of phenotypes in these species interaction with the wider community is required, several resources are currently in use by different resources and we require expert input to describe the phenotypes, but also to formalize the phenotypic descriptions. In order to make maximum use of existing terminologies (mouse phenotype, human phenotype ontology etc.) we will work with these communities to map between existing terms, provide new terms and also to annotate our datasets.

Work package number	WP7	Start date or starting event:	month 13		
Work package title	PhenoBridge-crossing the species bridge between mouse and human				
Activity Type	RTD				
Participant number	1:EMBL	11:HMGU	12: MUG	20: CRIMMP	
Person-months per participant	21	27	14	15	
Objectives					
Identify and develop a set of annotations, necessary terminologies, and mappings between terminologies for human and mouse models of diabetes and obesity					
Identify and group related interacting parameters in human and mouse which are involved in the development of clinical and molecular phenotypes					
Formalise rules for phenotypic annotation in human and mouse to work towards automation of phenotypic discovery and develop a related prototype service.					
Description of work and role of participants					

Task 1:

Analysis of existing mouse phenotype and human disease ontology terms, leading to submission of proposals for new terms to gather a comprehensive set of terms to describe diabetes and obesity phenotypes in mouse and human. As a first step, potentially relevant phenotypic parameters available from mouse high-throughput screening and in-depth phenotyping studies as well as from human studies across technologies such as gene expression and GWAS studies from the BioSD and metabolome profiles will be listed. For analysed parameters associated with diabetic/obese conditions that are not yet described appropriately in ontology terms, new terms have to be defined. A many to many mapping of phenotypic or diagnostic parameters onto ontology terms will be developed using the clinical expertise of scientists coming from the mouse or human diabetes and obesity fields. (EMBL-EBI, HMGU, MUG, CIRMMP).

Task 2:

Mapping of mouse and human phenotypes of diabetes and obesity. Based on the ontology terms developed in Task 1, observation patterns will be defined that describe clinical and molecular characteristics of diabetes and obesity phenotypes in mouse and human (EMBL-EBI, HMGU, MUG, CIRMMP). The identification of rules and criteria for identifying diabetes and obesity phenotypes (and how they map in mice and humans) will lead to a prototype for an automated procedure to identify phenotype matches across mouse and human (EMBL-EBI, HMGU, MUG, CIRMMP).